

Integrated pest management—diseases

Occurrence of teleomorph of *Fusarium graminearum* Schwabe, the causal agent of rice scab, in India

N. Iboton Singh and R. K. Tombisana Devi, Botany and Plant Pathology Department, College of Agriculture, Central Agricultural University, Iroisemba, Imphal 795001, Manipur, India

Fusarium graminearum Schwabe is one of the causal organisms of rice scab

(RSc). We collected black fungal fruiting bodies from completely rotted tissue of the uppermost leaf sheaths enclosing the panicles of rice variety Leima Phou during November 1993 in research plots of the College of Agriculture and in nearby farmers' fields (Fig. 1).

Fruiting bodies were separated from the rotted tissues, purified, and placed on potato dextrose agar to isolate the fungus. Leima Phou was inoculated at

booting with 5-d-old culture to prove pathogenicity.

We compared the conidial state (anamorph) of the fungus with those of pure cultures of *F. graminearum* and two other causal agents of RSc, *F. moniliforme* and *F. avenaceum*. We also studied the morphological characteristics of the perfect state (teleomorph) of the fungus from the diseased specimens.

The perithecia are superficial, spherical to ovoid, dark brown, and mostly $60-200 \times 60-192 \mu\text{m}$ in dimension. They have cylindrical to club-shaped asci, often slightly curved with a short stripe, and a thin undifferentiated wall measuring $60-83 \times 4-12 \mu\text{m}$. They have 8 distichous to obliquely monostichous ascospores. Ascospores are hyaline, curved fusoid with rounded ends, with 2-3 septate, measuring $19-28 \times 5-8 \mu\text{m}$ (Fig. 2).

The perithecial characteristics of the fungus were identified as *Gibberella zeae* (Schw.) Petch, the teleomorph of *F. graminearum*, which has been reported in the literature on a range of gramineous hosts except rice. The occurrence of the teleomorph of *F. graminearum* on rice constitutes the first report from India. ■

1. Black colored fruiting bodies of *Gibberella zeae* on rotted portions of a flagleaf sheath.

2. Asci of *G. zeae* outside the perithecium. The ascospores are diagonally oriented in each ascus.

Rice hull ash applied to soil reduces leaf blast incidence

C. T. Kumbhar and A. G. Nevase, Agricultural Research Station (ARS), Mahatma Phule Agricultural University Lonawala, 410401 Maharashtra, India; and N. K. Savant, International Fertilizer Development Center, Muscle Shoals, Alabama 35662, USA

Leaf blast caused by *Pyricularia oryzae* Cav. is a serious disease that can severely damage rice at the seedling stage. We investigated the effect of applying rice hull ash (RHA) to the soil in the seedbed on the incidence of leaf blast. The pot experiments were conducted in a greenhouse at ARS during the 1992 and 1993 wet seasons. Black to gray RHA (81.0% SiO_2), prepared by burning rice hulls in an open field, was amorphous with no peaks observed in X-ray